

Alternate Forms of the One-Way ANOVA F , Kruskal-Wallis K , and Partitional Clustering B

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Abstract

The one-way analysis of variance F statistic may be written entirely in terms of sample means without referencing the overall mean. There are good pedagogical reasons to use this alternate form. These comments also apply to the Kruskal-Wallis K , and the between sum of squares B statistic used in partitional clustering.

Key Words: Teaching, Intuition

1. One-Way ANOVA F

In the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test of the equality of population means the F statistic is typically represented as

$$F = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 \right] / (g-1)}{\hat{\sigma}^2} \quad (1)$$

Here, for sample i , n_i observations are observed with a sample mean \bar{x}_i and a sample standard deviation s_i . Also, g is the number of populations we are sampling from, with an overall sample average of

$$\bar{x} = \frac{n_1 \bar{x}_1 + n_2 \bar{x}_2 + \cdots + n_g \bar{x}_g}{n}$$

where $n = n_1 + n_2 + \cdots + n_g$ is the total sample size, and

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2 + \cdots + (n_g - 1)s_g^2}{n - g}$$

(the “mean squared error”) is a weighted average of the sample variances. If we have independent samples from normal populations with equal variances, then the p-value for the test

$$H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \cdots = \mu_g$$

$$H_a : \text{Not } H_0$$

is given by $P(F_{g-1, n-g} \geq F)$. We reject the null hypothesis when F is large.

Johnson (2022) gives

$$F = \frac{\left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i < j} n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)^2 \right]}{\hat{\sigma}^2} / (g-1) \quad (2)$$

as an equivalent, alternate form of F , and argues it may be preferred over the standard form of the F statistic in (1). An analogous alternate form of the Kruskal-Wallis statistic was also given in Johnson (2022).

2. Proof of the Equivalence of (1) and (2)

It is easiest to start with the expression in square brackets in (2).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i < j} n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)^2 &= \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^g n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^g n_i n_j \left[(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}) - (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x}) \right]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^g n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^g n_i n_j (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})^2 - 2 \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^g n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})(\bar{x}_j - \bar{x}) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum_{j=1}^g n_j + \sum_{i=1}^g n_i \sum_{j=1}^g n_j (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})^2 - 2 \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}) \sum_{j=1}^g n_j (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x}) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \left\{ n \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 + n \sum_{j=1}^g n_j (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x})^2 - 2 \cdot 0 \cdot 0 \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \left\{ 2n \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 \right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2 \end{aligned}$$

A proof of this result may also be found in Legendre and Fortin (2010).

3. Partitional Clustering B

With partitional clustering we attempt to partition data vectors into g groups where the data vectors in any one group are close in some sense. One approach is to use squared Euclidean distance to measure separation. In particular, the total variability in the data across all groups, T , may be decomposed into a sum of a within group variability, W , and a sum of between groups variability, B . In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \|x_{ij} - \bar{x}\|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \|x_{ij} - \bar{x}_i\|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^g n_i \|\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}\|^2 \\ &\equiv W + B \end{aligned}$$

Here, x_{ij} is the j th data vector in cluster i , and cluster i has n_i data points with mean \bar{x}_i , and \bar{x} is the overall mean across all n data points, $n = n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_g$. For a given dataset and value of g , T is fixed.

Given some partition of the data into g clusters, we cycle through the data points to see if moving a data point from its current cluster to some other cluster will reduce the within group variability or, equivalently, increase the between group variability. The algorithm terminates once a full cycle through the dataset yields no reallocation of a data point to a new cluster.

As before,

$$B = \sum_{i=1}^g n_i \|\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}\|^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i < j} n_i n_j \|\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j\|^2 \quad (3)$$

This right-hand expression for B , we claim, is a more intuitive collective measure of the variability (or separation) between groups.

More generally,

$$T = W + B$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (x_{ij} - \bar{x})(x_{ij} - \bar{x})' \\ W &= \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_i)(x_{ij} - \bar{x}_i)' \\ B &= \sum_{i=1}^g n_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})' = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i < j} n_i n_j (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)' \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and we claim that this right-most expression for B is more intuitive than the left-most expression.

The two expressions for B in (3) and in (4) may be shown to be equivalent using an argument nearly identical to that given in section 2 above. As an aside, (3) follows from the matrix expression for B in (4) upon taking the trace and then using the identity $tr(AA') = tr(A'A)$.

References

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